

**CONDITION OF ENGLISH AS
A SECOND LANGUAGE (ESL) IN
THE GOVT AIDED SCHOOLS
OF WEST BENGAL**

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Abstract

With a view to increase the student enrolment, decrease the rate of drop outs, create an exam free atmosphere, enable the learners to earn a sustainable livelihood after learning concerned regional language and vocational skill, the Govt of India adopted the No-Detention Policy (NDP) in 2009. The Govt of West Bengal introduced the policy in the state in 2010. Ever since its inception, the NDP has been subject to tremendous criticism from the end of the teachers who have always held that it would deteriorate the quality of education because it would generate a lethargy among the students those who work hard for a better result in one hand whereas in the other hand better students would not be properly rewarded. The teachers were feared to become apathetic to various learning issues. Such apprehensions have proved to be true. At the high school, level students are failing miserably. In West Bengal, results start to deteriorate from class IX, particularly in English. Students get promoted from Class I to Class IX without minimum knowledge of the language. Sometimes they even fail to write their own name correctly in English. Some prescribed texts are miles away from their familiar world. Yet, the pattern of the question paper is such that those students who even don't know to write their name in English manage to score handsome marks in exams. There is no doubt that learning to write one's own name is an activity that has to be covered at the lower primary level. The present paper tries to highlight the pathetic situation of English as the Second Language (ESL) at the Govt aided schools in West Bengal due to the NDP, negligence at the lower primary level and the strange question pattern system.

Keywords: English language, No Detention Policy.

INTRODUCTION

Students who got automatically promoted, as Karan Sabharwal

observes in 'No detention policy: Rethinking education system of India' faced "tough challenges when they reach class IX because safety net of no detention policy is till class VIII is not there. The policy has led to the development of lackadaisical attitude of stakeholders towards Indian education system."He felt,"A lot needs to be done and modification in the policy is required to improve the education system in the country and save the future of the country."

The condition of learning English as a second language in the state of West Bengal except major cities like Kolkata, Siliguri, Durgapur and so on projects a pathetic scenario. The researchers decided to portray the condition of English learning in Govt-aided schools. When they talked with the English teachers of different schools, they pointed out several factors behind this.

Sudipta Acharya,an Asst Teacher in English of Bandhnabagram Gandhi Vidyapith, says, "Due to the abolition of the Pass-Fail system, students have been getting promoted to the next class irrespective of the marks they score in the Summative Evaluations. Progress of students is very poor in almost every subject, particularly in English."

Abhijnan Chakraborty, another AT in English in Bolpur NNB High School points out, "Most of the pupils are first generation learners. There is none to guide them properly at their home. They do not get that much exposure to English what is required for. They have a prejudice that English is a difficult subject and cannot be managed easily."

"Modernized teaching learning materials are not applied by the government in case of English teaching. The teacher student ratio is more than 1: 40. So, it becomes difficult for the teachers to pay individual attention to every individual student. Although there is a provision for remedial classes, in many schools there is no para-teacher to conduct such classes," observes Debarati Sarkar, an AT of Beluti MKM High School.

Suparna Roy, of Bolpur NNB High School, is of opinion, "There has

always been a pressure from the guardians to complete the syllabus. Unit tests are also to be conducted at regular intervals. So remedial classes often become impossible to hold."

Ramranjan Chatterjee, Asst Teacher, Charkalgram High School, points out, "Nowadays teachers are burdened with many non-academic works like preparation of database for the Sabuj Sathi Project, Kanyashree project, list of Minority students, enlisting names for SC/ST categories. Naturally they also become exhausted at times. Moreover, in some cases, certain lessons have too long texts with too many exercises. The joy of learning on the part of the students naturally vanishes while dealing with such long lessons."

Roy says, "At the upper primary level, we get students who fail to introduce themselves in English." When asked how the students have been scoring considerable marks in the exams, Abhijnan Chakraborty, her colleague, says the questions are in most cases set in such a way that they score average marks. He further points out, when students encounter true or false type questions, they either write T or F. Often their responses are not correct but they manage to bag certain marks because at least one of their responses turns out to be correct if they write T/F in all the boxes provided for.

Mala Mallick says, the students respond the same way in case of the unseen passage also.

Suparna Roy remarks that cases are not rare the students misinterpret questions on story writing. She often comes across answer scripts where students take the outline of a story writing question as a 'fill in the blanks with appropriate articles and prepositions' type question and write articles and prepositions in between the hints of the question.

The researchers were unanimous that something must be done in the 7th or 8th period to find a way out. Some academically backward students are to be pointed out and certain initiatives should be taken experimentally to remedy the situation.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The present study will help to understand the progress of English learning as a second language in Govt-aided schools and hint at the solutions so that the avowed objective of teaching and learning of English may be successfully implemented in the English classes. Materialization of such objectives will ultimately enhance the learning outcome on the part of the students so far as the teaching-learning of English as a second language in the Govt aided schools of West Bengal is concerned.

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

Latu (1994) studied aiming to determine factors which might have impact on the learning of English as a second language macroskills (reading, writing, listening, and speaking) by Tongan secondary learners. The study was correlational in design and it worked from a synthetic perspective in that it looked at the way in which many aspects of language are interrelated to make the whole language system.

Subrahmanian (2003), attempted to show how movies, pop songs, and educational radio and television programs could be used in the language classroom to teach English. The demonstrations themselves were very popular and this was reflected in the fact that they earned high ratings on the end-of-course evaluation. The considerable amount of interaction that took place during these classes made them lively, and most teachers seemed to enjoy them.

Wold (2006) observes, "a learner who experiences difficulty and slow progress may not be aware of the causes or problems behind the lack of progress or how to resolve them. Instructors and directors of ESL programs might be unaware of the reasons for or resolutions to the difficulties a learner experience. It is crucial that ESL instructors... to determine the most likely reasons for their predicament and make recommendations, and if necessary, implement accommodations to help them overcome barriers to learning."

Hindi (2011) focused on building understanding how collaborative computing may be used with recommended teaching approaches in ESL courses to enhance student engagement and motivation.

Vijayalakshmi (2016) expresses the opinion, “the teaching learning of English as a subject at all levels of school education has mostly remained examination oriented. In most classrooms, English is taught as a subject based on rote learning rather than for language skills development which would be used by learners in real life situations.” She wanted to “provide an alternative mode of teaching to the teacher dominated Indian English classrooms where learners have very little opportunity for active participation and interaction with peers and the teacher in English classroom.”

Kumar (2016), in “Developing Speaking Skills of Senior Secondary Students an Exploratory Study” tried “to explore ways and means of helping senior secondary students improve their speaking skills.

Nath (2016), in “Problems In Teaching English In Secondary Schools In North Tripura District” expresses the opinion, “it is quite necessary to undertake a research work in the arena of the English Language Teaching (herein after referred to as “ELT”) at the secondary level in the North Tripura District in order to analytically detect the problems in the same field, thus providing logical solutions to them, so that the secondary level students of this district could be proficient in the English language, thereby being able to keep pace with the ongoing phenomena in the universe of knowledge in the era of globalisation.”

Adama (2019) says, “Learning a second language is never easy. Learning English as a second language is even less easy. Particularly if you are learning English outside of an English-speaking country. For instance, English language learners in African countries like Nigeria, Ghana, Liberia, Zambia, Malawi, and some other African countries face a lot of challenges because English is not the native language of these countries. Just as there are problems faced in learning English as foreign language, so there are challenges in learning English as second language.” He points out several factors

as hindrances to the teaching-learning of English as a second language. They are unqualified teachers, limited learning environment, lack of seriousness among learners, too much use of native language, too much dependence of learners on the teachers, dominance of advanced students in the classroom, and inadequate learning materials.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The researchers have chosen the present study in an attempt to see whether learning of English has been successful in generating such a classroom situation in West Bengal in which the teaching-learning system becomes more joyful, whether the learning outcome is satisfactory, whether the teachers have encountered any hindrance in using it and what sort of help is received from the Govt to carry on the project.

DELIMITATION

The study was delimited to the academically backward students of Class V to Class IX of Bolpur NNB High School.

METHODOLOGY

The researchers have followed the Descriptive Survey Method. It is a method which is "aimed at casting light on current issues or problems through a process of data collection that enables them to describe the situation more completely than was possible without employing this method." (Fox, W. & Bayat, M.S. (2007) "A Guide to Managing Research" Juta Publications, p.45)

OBJECTIVES

The present study aims to evaluate

- Whether the students are able to comprehend the ESL text books provided by the Govt.
- Whether the present method of teaching ESL is sufficient for the learners.

- Whether the students can comprehend and respond to questions related to their surrounding in ESL
- Whether the learners are familiar at all with the English alphabet.
- Whether the teachers are equipped with adequate TLM's to achieve the desired end.
- What are the difficulties in achieving the desired end?
- How such hindrances can be resolved.

ANALYSIS OF THE OBJECTIVE

The ESL text book is provided by the Govt. the book is carefully designed with texts and exercises by a team of chosen experts. The present study aims to find out whether such textbooks are successful in attaining success so far as learning of ESL is concerned.

There are several factors of teaching ESL. At present in West Bengal, the Functional Communicative Approach is followed. The present study wants to find out whether the approach serves the purpose.

Any language learning is an LSRW skill. The present study seeks to analyse whether the learners are able to listen and read aloud/ silently and answer to the questions set for a test.

In an age of moral degeneration, the researchers want to find out whether the learners are acquainted with the idea of moral values and can respond accordingly in ESL when the situation demands.

The paper wants to find out whether the learners possess very simple concepts of grammar and the strength of their vocabulary.

Another objective of this study is to find out whether there is sufficient TLM for the teachers to improve the level of learning on the part of the learners. It will try to see whether the teachers themselves devise certain TLM's to overcome the situation.

There are other hindrances also, like, disinterested students, low enrolment, unavailability of modern facilities etc. The study will not

neglect such issues.

The study will also try to find out ways to solve such hindrances.

DETAILED DESCRIPTION OF THE WORK

So, the researchers decided to find out whether the students have any competency to express minimum information regarding themselves and their families in English or not. If they respond satisfactorily, it may be taken for granted that they have the ability to read a passage, comprehend it and express themselves accordingly.

The following students were selected from different classes of Bolpur NNB High School on the basis of their poor performance in previous Unit Tests:

Sl No	Name	Class	Section	Roll No
01	RANJAN SUTRADHAR	7	A	26
02	ABHI MURMU	7	A	41
03	SOUNAK CHATTERJEE	7	A	33
04	SOVON GHOSH	7	A	55
05	SHUBHAM GUPTA	7	A	38
06	DEEP GHOSH	7	A	40
07	MAHIMUDDIN SK	7	A	44
08	PRABHAT GARAI	7	B	40
09	SAKHAWAT SK	8	A	45
10	SK NUR ISLAM	8	B	55
11	RAKESH HAZRA	8	B	57
12	SK ARKAT AJID	8	A	82
13	GOUTAM GOSWAMI	8	A	77
14	SAHEB KHAN	8	A	74
15	PRAKASH DUTTA	8	A	50
16	AJJUL MOLLA	8	A	59
17	SABIRUDDIN KHAN	8	A	61
18	SAHIL HAQUE	8	A	48
19	AMIT KUMAR BHAKAT	9	B	29
20	SHIBNATH SARKAR	9	B	53
21	ROHIT SINGH	9	B	51
22	Likenath Bagdi	9	B	55
23	MD OWASEF AJJI	9	B	58
24	PARTHO MAJHI	9	B	83
25	AJAY SINGH	9	B	68
26	AMIT KUMAR MONDAL	9	B	41
27	BINOD DAS	9	B	45
28	LAXMAN SINGH	9	B	88

Their first task was to fill in the blanks:

I am My father's name is
 he is a My
 mother is a her name is
 We live at In

The task was designed to test the ability of the students to read a paragraph and filling up the missing links which are nouns and which they are familiar with. It was aimed to testify their competence to supply information about themselves.

When they submitted their responses, it was found that none of them could supply all the information about their own selves. The following chart shows a statistical analysis in this regard:

Criteria	No of students who succeeded to supply the information	Remarks
Own name	28	
Father's name	28	2 entries in Bengali
Father's occupation	8	
Mother's occupation	8	
Mother's name	11	1 entry in Bengali
Name of locality they live	2	
Name of the town/village	1	

In certain cases, wrong entries were also found. The following table gives an idea of such wrong entries:

Entry demanded	Entry made	Made by
Occupation of mother	Name of mother	Sakhawat Sk, Shubham Gupta, Deep Ghosh, Saheb Khan, Prakash Dutta, Ajijul Molla, Sabiruddin Khan, Prabhat Garai
Name of locality	Name of father	Sakhawat Sk
Name of town/village	Name of father	Sakhawat Sk
Father's occupation	Mother's name	Sk Nur Islam, Rakesh Hazra

Parho Majhi did not know the English spelling of his father's name, and, Deep Ghosh did not know the English spellings of both his parents. Both of them used Bengali letters to respond.

The second task was designed to test the ability of the students in filling up forms by supplying information about their families:

Number of family members	Information			
Number of earning members				
Number of siblings	Brother		Sisters	
How many of them go to school				
Do your grandparents live with you	Yes/No			
Type of your house	Personal/ Rented			
Number of rooms in your house				
How do you eat	Sitting on the floor/ dining table			
Is there any bathroom in your house	Yes/ No			
Who cooks at your house				
What is used to cook at your house	Gas/ Stove/ Chula			

After the completion of the task, the correct entries were sought. What was found is given in the following table.

Criteria	Correct entries			
Number of family members	5			
Number of earning members	1			
Number of siblings	Brother	3	Sisters	4
How many of them go to school	1			
Do your grandparents live with you	17			
Type of your house	12			
Number of rooms in your house	3			
How do you eat	18			
Is there any bathroom in your house	18			
Who cooks at your house	4			
What is used to cook at your house	18			

Such analysis proves that the pupils don't have minimum knowledge about themselves and their families. They are incapable of expressing certain data in English although they have the information sought for. These two tasks are referred in the next section as the task of Day 1.

It may be pointed out in this context that the students seem to be very uneasy with the items, they tried to seek help from others, and, after repeated requests for submission of their answer scripts, they submitted the papers.

Accordingly, it was resolved that the students must be equipped with

- The correct English spellings of their parents' names.
- An awareness of the various professions their parents may be engaged in
- An idea of the number of their family members
- The concept of the earning member
- The ability to trace the earning member of the family
- The concept of siblings
- The capability to count their siblings gender wise
- An awareness of what personal home and rented house mean
- The competency to count the number of rooms in their houses
- The notion of eating style
- The meaning of 'cooking'
- The concept of different kinds of fuel used in cooking

Several extra classes were taken to impart the pupils the above parameters. The learners participated enthusiastically. The teaching-learning procedure was made enjoyable as much as possible.

Of course, it was not easy for the teacher to acquaint the pupils with all the items. Learners took time to understand and to master the spellings. The teachers also kept patience so that the final outcome might be satisfactory.

DAY1

Students were given two tasks related to their personal self and their family. The responses of the students were analysed.

DAY2

Students were individually attended to acquaint them with the spellings of the names of themselves, their parents, their locality, town/village.

DAY3

Students were introduced to the names of different professions. Then they were asked to identify the profession of their parents. They were told to remember the spelling of those names of professions.

DAY4

Students were introduced with the concept of family, family members, earning member, grandparents. To facilitate their understanding, pictures given below were utilized:
Learners were further provided with the idea of siblings, school going, bathroom, rooms in a house, eating place, cooking person and cooking fuel.

DAY5

The pupils were once again subjected to the same tasks as on Day 1. They were found to be at ease with the items provided. They took less time to respond this time. They were, at the same time, very happy to do these tasks.

Of course, the same number of students were not available. The final assessment was carried out with the students present on that particular day.

This time it was found that the pupils made almost all the responses

correctly except a few minor mistakes like confusing small and capital letters.

This sample gave an idea that most of the students are weak in English. While searching for the actual causes of weakness in English the researchers decided to find out whether the students of junior classes could write the English alphabet correctly. Another sample of students was selected from different classes of the school:

Name	Class	Section	Roll No
Debjit Das	V	A	21
Babu Das	V	A	19
Partha Ghosh	V	A	51
Dibakar Pal	V	B	85
Surojit Birbanshi	VI	B	42
Rajib Konra	VI	B	59
Rohit Sk	VI	B	62
Ramkrishna Sutradhar	VI	B	21
Souvik Garai	VI	B	45

The first task was to write the English alphabet in capital and small letters. When they submitted the paper, it was found that most of the students could not write English alphabet correctly. It was found only 4 out of 10 students could write the English alphabet correctly.

Debjit Das of class V-A wrote only 4 letters.

Surojit Birbanshi could not write the alphabets in order.

Babu Das failed to write the alphabets in small letter.

Souvik Garai wrote a few from the two.

Rajib Konra could not write the letters properly.

Rohit Sk wrote the letter q like p.

Accordingly, it was determined that the students must be furnished with the following:

A. To write the alphabet correctly and in order.

B. To give a minimum gap between letters.

C. To pronounce the letter correctly.

D. To practice handwriting in four lined pages.

Several extra classes were taken to impart the above lessons. The learners participated enthusiastically. They had the urge to learn from the teacher. The teacher also wrote the alphabet in their copies and tried to acquaint the learners with all the items.

Students were individually attended so that they could write the alphabet correctly and in order.

When they were given the same task again. This time it was found that the students were happy to complete the task. They took less time to complete the tasks.

CONCLUSION

The tedious project ultimately hints at the following points:

- Proper care is not taken at the primary level in teaching ESL.
- Texts are to be designed in such a way so that the students feel familiarity with the texts.
- There should be more and more interesting stories to keep the mind of the learner attentive all the time.
- Compatibility of certain texts with the target learners must be revised. For example, the text of Lesson 1 in the text book of class VII contains so many long sentences that students become disinterested while dealing with that text. The same can be said for 'Mowgli Among the Wolves' of the same class.

- The mistakes that the students commit at the upper primary or secondary level regarding their names and families have to be rectified at the primary level. There should be a monitoring and sudden visit by the higher authority to see whether the pupils can at least know and express in English something about their family.
- More and more emphasis must be laid on improving the skill of expression in English of the students.
- More and more exposure to English is necessary. The teachers should provide an English listening atmosphere in the classroom.
- Proper and modernized TLM's should be provided by the governments to the schools for making teaching of English effective for the students.
- If language learning is an LSRW skill, spoken English must be given due importance.
- Textbooks for classes VII and VIII are overloaded with too many exercises whereas the textbook of Class X is much easier. Such imbalanced distribution should be taken care of.
- If textbooks are to be revised, thorough research must be made with students belonging to semi-urban and rural schools. The opinions of the teachers of such schools must be given priority instead of the teachers and students of metropolitan schools.
- Questions are to be set in such a way so that the actual comprehension level can be assessed. 'Uplifting the percentage of passed and promoted students' must be discarded.

Thus there are various concerns in teaching of English as well as what best can be done to assist students learning & English and the students performance in English learning shall improve.

PERSONS CONTACTED

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